

Figure S1. The sunburst plot representing the distribution of HAD-superfamily proteins (Interproscan ID:IPR023214) within 41132 species spanning the four superkingdoms of life. The size of the segments correspond to 502 protein sequences and the segment representing *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is highlighted by the black arrow.

A

B

Figure S2. (A) NMR spectrum of the Pald intermediate diethyl (2-oxoethyl)-phosphonate. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.68 (td, $J = 3.2, 0.9$ Hz, 1H), 4.23 – 4.13 (m, 4H), 3.09 (dd, $J = 21.9, 3.3$ Hz, 2H), 1.36 (t, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 6H). **(B) NMR spectrum of the sodium salt of Pald.** ^1H NMR (400 MHz, D_2O) δ 9.61 (broadened t, $J = 4.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.02 (dd, $J = 20.8, 3.9$ Hz, 2H).

A i. TCS

Figure S3. Resistance to Polymyxin B (PMP) in PAO1 and mutants determined by using liquid cultures or E-strips. Light green: 0 mM Ca²⁺, dark green: 5 or 10 mM Ca²⁺. **(A) Role of previously characterized two component systems (i) and efflux pumps (ii) in Ca²⁺ induced PMB resistance.** Cells were grown without or with 5 mM Ca²⁺, normalized to OD₆₀₀ of 0.1, and plated onto BMM agar plates with the corresponding concentration of Ca²⁺. E-strips with gradient of PMB were placed on the bacterial lawns. MIC was recorded after 24 h incubation (n=3). **(B) MIC assay for liquid cultures of PAO1 and complemented random mutagenesis mutants.** The cultures were grown without or with 10 mM Ca²⁺, normalized to OD₆₀₀ of 0.3, normalized, and inoculated into the corresponding media at 1:100 ratio. 200 µl of this culture were added to each well of 96 well plate without or with PMB at different concentrations. Plates were incubated at 37° C with fast shaking in Biotek plate reader. The MIC was recorded after 24 h incubation (n=3). **(C) Role of the genes identified by random mutagenesis in Ca²⁺ induced PMB resistance.** Cells were prepared and MIC were determined as in (A) (n=3). Student t-test; **P* value < 0.05. **(D) PMB susceptibility testing of clean deletion mutants Δ *pcrP* (Δ PA2803), Δ PA3237 and Δ PA5317.** Cells were prepared and MIC were determined as in (A) (n=3). Two-way Anova; *****P* value < 0.0001. **(E-G) Comparison of growth in Δ *pcrP* (Δ PA2803) (E), Δ PA3237 (F), and Δ PA5317 (G) strains to WT PAO1.** Cells were grown for 12 h without Ca²⁺, normalized to OD₆₀₀ = 0.1, and inoculated into 100 mL BMM medium (1:1000 dilution). The cultures were incubated at 37°C, 200 rpm for 24 h, and OD₆₀₀ was monitored over time (n=3).

A**PA2803**

Figure S4. In-silico analysis. (A) Schematic presentation of primary sequence of PcrP (PA2803) (9-205, Blue, conserved hydrolase domain, CDD database), PA3237 (13-35, Orange, transmembrane helix, TMHMM v. 2.0), and PA5317 (3-525 Grey, periplasmic DppA like component of ABC transporter, 26-509, light box, PBP2-DppA like region, 404, 408, 421-424, 426, small boxes, polypeptide binding sites, CDD database). (B) Structure prediction by i-Tasser. Predicted 3D structure of **i.** PA2803 (TM score 0.951, Ca²⁺ binding C score 0.33), **ii.** PA3237 (TM score 0.5) and **iii.** PA5317 (TM score 0.94 and peptide binding C score 0.62). The modeling was done by PyMOL.

Figure S5. Role of PcrP in growth, production of polyp, and virulence factor production during P_i starvation in *Pa*. (A) Growth yield of WT and $\Delta pcrP$ strains during growth at low P_i . Cells were grown at low P_i (50 μ M), normalized to OD₆₀₀ of 0.3, and inoculated at 0.1% into low P_i BMMH8 with no or 5 mM Ca^{2+} . These cultures were grown for 38 h at 37°C shaking at 200 rpm and OD₆₀₀ was monitored (n=3). (B) P_i uptake of WT, $\Delta pcrP$ and $\Delta pcrP::pcrP$ strains during growth at low P_i . Cells were grown at low P_i (50 μ M) with no or 5 mM Ca^{2+} , and samples collected over time. The supernatants of these samples were subjected to P_i quantification using malachite green reagent. The P_i uptake was normalized by OD₆₀₀. Depicted here is the normalized P_i uptake of the three strains at 22 h (in mid-log phase) (n=3). Light blue; 0 mM Ca^{2+} , dark blue; 5 mM Ca^{2+} . Two-way ANOVA; *** p-value \leq 0.001, ** p-value \leq 0.01 (C) Ca^{2+} -dependent changes in OL production in WT and $\Delta pcrP$ strains during stationary phase growth at low P_i . Cells were grown at low P_i (50 μ M) without or with 5 mM Ca^{2+} in BMMH8 for 38 h at 37°C shaking at 200 rpm, and OD₆₀₀ and total lipids were extracted using Blich-Dyer method. Organically dissolved lipids were separated by TLC on a silica plate using a solvent system. OLs were detected by applying the Ninhydrin reagent. (Representative of an experiment done in triplicate). (D) Changes in pyocyanin abundance in WT, $\Delta pcrP$ and $\Delta pcrP::pcrP$ strains during stationary phase at low P_i . Cells were grown at low P_i (50 μ M) without or with 5 mM Ca^{2+} in BMMH8 for 38 h at 37°C shaking at 200 rpm. Pyocyanin was extracted from culture supernatants collected after 38 h using chloroform and 0.2 M HCl. The absorbance of pyocyanin was read at 520 nm and normalized by OD₆₀₀ (n=3). Student t-test; ** p-value \leq 0.01

Figure S6. (A) Phosphonate assays conducted with purified PcrP and Pald as the substrate. 50 μM 6xHis-PcrP was subjected to enzyme assays with 1 mM Pald as substrate. The release of acetaldehyde was detected by measuring the absorbance at 340 nm at RT (ϵ , 6200 M cm⁻¹). The enzymatic conversion of NADH by alcohol dehydrogenase enzyme when acetaldehyde is present was monitored as shown in the schematic representation of the chemical reaction. The positive control contained acetaldehyde with NADH and alcohol dehydrogenase (n=3). **(B) Phosphatase assays conducted with purified PcrP and pNPP as the substrate.** The hydrolysis of pNPP to pNP (ϵ , 18.4 mM cm⁻¹) was monitored at RT in the presence of 1 unit of shrimp alkaline phosphatase (black squares) or PcrP (blue circles) by measuring the absorbance at 410 nm for 30 min. The experiment was performed in triplicate with one representative result shown.

Figure S7. Molecular dynamics of PA3518, Acp3 and their complexes with PcrP. (A) PA3518 and (B) Acp3 form stable dimers. (C) Molecular dynamics of hetero-hexamer PcrP-PA3518-Acp3 complex. (C) AlphaFold predicted complex is unstable (D) Manually prepared complex shows stable interactions of Acp3. There two-colored chains indicate two different units in a dimeric complex, at the start of the MD simulations. The grey structures indicate the conformation at the end of 1 μ s MD simulation.

Figure S8. Interactions of PcrP with self (A), PA3518 (B) and Acp3 (C). The interaction energies are calculated using molecular dynamics simulations and averaged over Pcp3 length (247 residues). Higher negative values indicate stronger interaction.

A

Figure S9. Simultaneous binding of PcrP and KatA to Acp3 appears unlikely. (A) The predicted binding of PcrP to Acp3, (B) The predicted binding of KatA to Acp3. (C) Simultaneous binding of PcrP and KatA is not feasible due to large steric clashes and significant overlap in structures.

